

CHEMISTRY

CHARACTERISTICS OF METHANOL CONVERSION TO DIMETHYL ETHER OVER ZEOLITE CATALYSTS

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Abstract

Production of dimethyl ether (DME), introduced as an alternative fuel to address the widespread use of fossil fuels, takes place through direct and indirect synthesis. The direct synthesis of DME combines methanol (CH_3OH) formation, integrating both redox and acidic sites. The indirect method includes a two-stage process, starting with CH_3OH synthesis from syngas ($\text{CO} + \text{H}_2$) over $\text{Cu}/\text{ZnO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts, following dehydration over acidic catalysts to form DME.

The purpose of the paper was to study the conversion of CH_3OH to DME and hydrocarbons on Al_2O_3 and H-forms of ZSM-5 zeolite, also modified with phosphoric acid. It was suggested that the formation of C_2H_4 in a structure-sensitive reaction occurs with the participation of the Brønsted acid center and the Lewis basic center.

Keywords: CH_3OH , Al_2O_3 , ZSM-5 zeolite, catalyst, conversion, DME, C_2H_4 , olefins, hydrocarbons.

INTRODUCTION

The most rational technique for obtaining various hydrocarbons from natural gas, which is available in abundance, includes the sequential transformation of CH_4 through synthesis gas type catalysts involves a preliminary stage of dehydration to DME. Hence, the corresponding final products can likewise be achieved from this compound [2, p. 295].

It is evident that the increased attention in DME production as a green energy carrier defines its prospects [11, p.3]. In this respect, innovative catalysts are being advanced, or mechanical mixtures of catalysts are used for the conversion of $\text{CO} + \text{H}_2$ to CH_3OH and its dehydration into DME [12, p. 440] [10, p. 3] [9, p. 29]. This initiative lessens the requirements for $\text{CO} + \text{H}_2$, simplifying the production technology, thereby lowering the product cost. Therefore, combining the processes of derived CH_3OH with its dehydration to DME is considered a flexible way to enhance the competence of hydrocarbons obtained from natural gas over those from oil.

An effective solution to the integration problem of the above processes with the use of DME requires the selection or synthesis of new catalysts with high efficiency to acquire higher hydrocarbons for the selective conversion of $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{DME}$ and $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{DME} \rightarrow$ corresponding hydrocarbons. The possibility of combining these technologies into current petrochemical and energy infrastructures can play a decisive role in reducing dependence on crude oil for hydrocarbon production.

PURPOSE. THE URGENCY OF THE PROBLEM

For a long time, the building block of global energy production has been associated with fossil fuels,

however, their utilization is bringing increasingly severe environmental impacts with itself. Burning coal, oil, and natural gas results in the release of massive amounts of CO_2 and other GHGs, causing climate change and global warming. Around 70% of the world's total GHG emissions come from CO_2 due to the combustion of fossil fuels. Beyond pollution, fossil fuels are a major contributor to climate change due to their role in the increasing amount of GHGs. When combusted, coal, oil, and natural gas release significant CO_2 and CH_4 gases, two of the most potent GHGs inducing heat trap in the Earth's atmosphere. This initiates rising global temperatures, extreme climatic conditions, rising sea levels, and melting glaciers. During the last century, the continuous dependence on fossil fuels has considerably increased atmospheric CO_2 concentrations, affecting the amplification of wildfires, hurricanes, heatwaves, and droughts. [5, p. 258-274]

DME achieves progressive recognition as a clean and versatile energy alternative, that can replace traditional fuels in a variety of applications. This recognition stems from its unique chemical and physical properties. Its potential as a flexible energy carrier and an alternative fuel is enhanced by its green properties, such as sulfur-free combustion and low particulate emissions. In contrast to traditional hydrocarbons, DME possesses a high cetane number, lacking C-C bonds, which contributes to its clean combustion profile. A distinguishably significant feature of DME is its oxygen content of as high as 35%, enabling smokeless combustion of the fuel and reduced NO_x and sulfur oxide SO_x , and particulate matter. It is considered a viable replacement for diesel fuel in compression ignition engines with its physical features allowing for straightforward integration into current LPG infrastructure. Beyond its utilization as a motor fuel, DME can function

as a fuel for power plants and as an intermediary product easily converting into gasoline, attributed to enhanced ecological properties with minimum undesirable impurities. In addition, DME can be applied as an environmentally friendly refrigerant, especially regarding its impact on the ozone layer of the atmosphere. [3, p. 55-58]

EXPERIMENTAL PART

The study objects were samples developed by granular zeolite of the HZSM-5 (ZSM-5) type ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 50$). The granules formed underwent air drying at between 90–120°C with following calcination at 550°C (5 h). Part of the catalyst granulated was additionally treated with an aqueous phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) solution with stirring at 80–95°C (3 h) and then subjected to the same drying and calcination processes. The resulting samples contained 5 wt.% phosphorus, calculated as P_2O_5 .

The catalyst samples were tested in a flow-through fixed-bed setup with a 10 g catalyst load at atmospheric pressure, temperatures of 280–450°C, and a liquid CH_3OH feed rate of 4–12 h^{-1} . The catalyst was pre-treated with air for 1 h at temperatures 50–100°C higher

than the reaction temperature with purging the system by a N_2 stream (0.5 h) afterwards, until the desired temperature was established.

The CH_3OH conversion products were analyzed under gas chromatography through Auto System XL (Perkin Elmer) and Gasochrom.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In accordance with the paper [16, p. 23] and our data (Fig. 1), Al_2O_3 demonstrates consistently high activity in CH_3OH conversion with selective DME formation. The conversion of CH_3OH under similar terms on zeolite catalysts becomes more complex. As shown in Fig. 1, a, CH_3OH is converted to hydrocarbons on the H-form of ZSM-5 zeolite, displaying high selectivity and conversion rate in the first 10 minutes of the experiment. However, after 30 minutes of catalysis process, the activity of the catalyst drastically decreases (Fig. 1, b), and DME becomes the primary product.

The fluctuation in the catalytic activity of ZSM-5 zeolite poses a challenge in terms of its modification. Considering the acid-type catalyst activity in these reactions, additional studies of CH_3OH conversion were conducted on the treated samples with H_3PO_4 .

Fig. 1. The effect of experiment duration (a – 10 min; b – 30 min) on CH_3OH conversion on the initial catalysts (1); the selectivity of DME formation (2) and hydrocarbons (3); $T = 350^\circ\text{C}$, space velocity 3 h^{-1} .

Fig. 2. The effect of experiment duration (a – 10 min; b – 120 min) on CH_3OH conversion on catalysts treated with phosphoric acid (1) and the selectivity of DME formation (2) and hydrocarbons (3); $T = 350^\circ\text{C}$, space velocity = 3 h^{-1} .

Weighing the data in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, it should be noted that the H_3PO_4 introduction into Al_2O_3 made nearly no impact on its characteristics in CH_3OH conversion. On the other hand, the treatment of zeolites with H_3PO_4 modified their catalytic properties.

The catalyst testing depicted the retainment of its activity up to 10 h^{-1} of feed rates. Hence, following P_2O_5 introduction, zeolite Y-based catalysts, in combination with higher selectivity for DME, demonstrated an enhanced productivity, making them promise to produce DME from synthesis gas alongside $\text{CO} + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ conversion catalysts.

The ZSM-5 modification with H_3PO_4 positively affects its catalytic features in CH_3OH conversion. As shown in Fig. 2, this effect primarily balances the high catalyst activity in converting CH_3OH to higher hydrocarbons.

The contact of strongly bound CH_3OH (methoxonium groups) (I) with a second CH_3OH molecule from the gas phase brings an intermediate state formation with itself which includes bond transfer. The decomposition of this intermediary leads to DME and H_2O formation.

Therefore, the CH_3OH conversion product yield relies upon the zeolite structural type. A comparison of

Based on this scheme, the first alcohol molecule activation occurs on the B-site (ZOH). Then, according to [7, p. 295], the DME molecules produced can contact

When it comes to this process occurring on Al_2O_3 , the desorption of the DME molecules formed from its pores is not impeded. However, in the case of narrower-pored ZSM-5 zeolite, where both $(\text{Z}_1\text{Z}_2)\text{O}$ and B-sites (ZOH) are apparent in the micropores, the interaction

with similar sites, e.g., adsorb in accordance with scheme (2), forming an intermediary (II).

of intermediate II with the strongly adsorbed methoxonium group I can occur, resulting in the formation of an activated complex (III) based on scheme (3).

The bond redistribution in this complex substance, with the water molecule release, induces the formation of a new complex (IV), decomposing with the C_2H_4 release. In scheme (3), it is significant that the C_2H_4 formation is accompanied by the transition of the B-site to

the L-site:

Such an alteration in surface properties is essential for the conduct of catalytic processes, being the subject of further investigation.

Table 1

Effect of water on the yield of DME conversion products on ZSM-5; $T = 450^{\circ}\text{C}$; space velocity 1 h^{-1}

Reaction mixture	Transformation products, %C				
	C_2H_4	C_3H_6	C_4	C_5	C_{5+}
DME: $\text{N}_2 = 1:1$	6	26	22	15	20
(DME: $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 1:1$): N_2	6	36	23	14	8

Therefore, the bond redistribution, illustrated in scheme (3), suggests a possible primary C–C bond formation stage that is the limiting factor in the CH_3OH conversion to hydrocarbons. This assertion is that ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$) dehydration to C_2H_4 , unlike CH_3OH , straightforwardly occurs on Al_2O_3 and zeolite Y [8, p. 7740].

Based on the scheme (3), the process on ZSM-5 is consistent with the defined concepts of the involvement of three CH_3OH molecules in the C_2H_4 formation [14, p. 44–45] [14, p. 9085] and an intermediary similar in structure to methoxyethane [3, p. 58] [15, p. 15260]. Hence, the distances between B-sites (ZOH) and L-sites ($\text{Z}_1\text{Z}_2\text{O}$), constrained by the dimensional parameters of the zeolite micropores, support the formation of activated complexes III. Furthermore, based on the data obtained, it can be summarized that as the diameter of the micropore lowers from 0.55 nm (ZSM-5), the feasibility of generating such a complex rise to a limiting value (DME absence in the products), hence defining

the structural sensitivity of primary C_2H_4 formation during CH_3OH and DME conversion.

From this perspective, it is also noteworthy that regarding narrower-pored zeolites such as SAPO-34 and SAPO-17 (pore diameters 0.32–0.38 nm), the assumption of C_2H_4 formation via $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (via two CH_3OH molecules) [1, p.139] can likewise be depicted by scheme (3). However, due to the smaller distances between B-sites and L-sites in comparison with ZSM-5, the role of CH_3OH (methoxonium) in intermediates I and III is replaced by H_2O molecule (hydroxonium).

The CH_3OH conversion on H-ZSM-5 zeolite to higher hydrocarbons includes the DME and primary C_2H_4 formation in respective order. Despite that, as shown in Fig. 3, the distribution of hydrocarbon products from CH_3OH and DME conversion varies under similar conditions. If CH_3OH fundamentally yields low-molecular-weight olefins, the DME conversion mainly produces higher-molecular-weight aliphatic hydrocarbons of isostructure.

Fig. 3. Distribution (selectivity of formation) of methanol and DME conversion products on ZSM-5 catalyst ($T = 375^{\circ}\text{C}$, space velocity = 3 h^{-1}): 1 – $\text{C}_1\text{--}\text{C}_3$ alkanes; 2 – $\text{C}_2\text{=}\text{C}_4$ olefins; 3 – C_4+ aliphatic hydrocarbons; 4 – aromatic hydrocarbons; 5 – DME.

During CH_3OH conversion to hydrocarbons, twice as much H_2O is released compared to the DME conversion. In this regard, it is valuable to consider the H_2O effect released during the conversion of CH_3OH on the yield of DME conversion products.

Table 1 presents data on the distribution of DME conversion products (without H_2O and with H_2O dilution) as an example. A comparison illuminates that additional H_2O (corresponding to the amount released during 100% CH_3OH conversion, DME: $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 1:1$) influences the yield of conversion results. It can be noted that under the introduced water vapor effect, the propylene yield increases, while the C_2H_4 yield remains consistent in practice. Furthermore, there is an almost twofold reduction in the C_{5+} hydrocarbon formation.

Hence, the additional introduction of H_2O does not affect the C_2H_4 yield with only influencing its following

oligomerization, decreasing the yield of higher-molecular-weight hydrocarbons. Moreover, it is important to highlight that H_2O vapor, while inhibiting the oligomerization of the formed low-molecular-weight olefins, does not affect the primary C_2H_4 alkylation. Variation of the ratio of DME (CH_3OH): H_2O , to purposefully adjust the hydrocarbon product yield from their conversion becomes feasible.

CONCLUSION

The yield of hydrocarbon products can be purposefully controlled by varying the ratio of DME (CH_3OH): H_2O .

Another conclusion from the analysis of the obtained results is that if the C_2H_4 formation from CH_3OH or DME can be characterized by structurally sensitive reactions depending on the distances between B-sites

(ZOH) and L-sites (Z_1Z_2O), constrained by the dimensional parameters of zeolite micropores between 0.32 and 0.55 nm, then the reactions of other hydrocarbon formation become structurally insensitive, and their yield can be adjusted by selecting both conditions and catalysts for the conversion of CH_3OH and DME.

The examination of the results obtained and literature data indicates that the C_2H_4 formation is a structurally sensitive reaction, including Brønsted acid sites and Lewis basic sites of the catalyst, and is determined by the distance between these sites. Since the diameter of the zeolite micropores lessens from 0.55 nm (ZSM-5) to 0.38 nm (SAPO-34), there is a replacement of one of the CH_3OH molecules by H_2O molecule during the primary C_2H_4 formation.

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